

CURING THE CURRICULUM

Students' Take on Medical Education

Episode [8]: Why we need leaders who actually care — Joshua Hartzell #CTC8

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ABOUT THIS PODCAST

Curing the Curriculum is a student-led co-creation podcast that tries to bridge the research-to-practice gap in (medical) education. We aim to translate cutting-edge research into accessible conversations with actionable insights for students, educators, clinicians and anyone else interested.

TRANSCRIPT DISCLAIMER

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EPISODE TRANSCRIPT

Ulf Ebeling (00:35)

Welcome back everyone. For the first time ever also as a video podcast, and today we're being joined by a very special guest, Dr. Joshua Hartzell, an experienced internal medicine and infectious diseases physician and retired army colonel who spent over 25 years in military medicine. Josh draws on his very rich background in clinical care, leadership and medical education.

to teach practical, caring-inspired leadership strategies for healthcare. And he has written a book, *A Prescription for Caring in Healthcare Leadership*, with an actual prescription on the cover, which I absolutely love, like you literally give people a old-fashioned maybe prescription. And in the book, he offers evidence-based insights on building cultures of compassion and excellence by prioritizing

the well-being of healthcare teams to ultimately improve patient care. Josh is also a sought after speaker and coach on leadership development and faculty at the MGH Institute of Health Professions in Boston. Josh, welcome. And to maybe start us off, I was interested what your favorite thing is to bake?

Josh Hartzell (01:46)

~ Great question. Well, Ulf thanks for having me and thanks for the work you're doing I think this is such a great podcast with a sort of unique Audience and I love the work you're doing. So thank you for that The the favorite thing I love to bake. Well, can I give I'm gonna give two the first would be I am a huge chocolate chip cookie addict So any chocolate chip cookie is probably my favorite thing to bake

I will say the second one given the time of year since we're in December is that ~ my kids and I will be baking sugar cookies and decorating them this weekend. It's kind of a family tradition. So cookies, in chocolate chip generally over the holidays, it's definitely sugar cookie time.

Ulf Ebeling (02:31)

sounds sounds very good. Well, you talk about your habits and that you like baking in your book, but it's just not random that you talk about this, right? I think it's in the context of self-care and that might be a bit counterintuitive for someone listening. Well, if you're leader you need to lead others. Why does it maybe all start with self-care?

Josh Hartzell (02:55)

Yeah, and that's one of the main reasons why I put that chapter in the book is because when we think about leadership, we very often think about all the people we're leading. And what I've seen over, you know, personally my career, but others careers is that when we don't take care of ourselves, it really impacts how we are able to effectively lead others. And, you know, most of the leadership books that are written are written in that outward perspective of what am I going to do for others? And I thought it was important

and especially we think about burnout also, to have a chapter that was just dedicated to how do you take care of yourself and what does that look like? And one of the things that I tell people is that's different for everybody. Like I can't define for you like what your self-care looks like. I mean there are certain things that we all need like sleep, good nutrition, but then there are other areas in our lives that just are gonna be unique. Yeah, so for me, I love to cook, I like to bake. ~

And I do those things because one, like the end product that I get to eat. But I also just find it sort of relaxing to spend, you know, an afternoon putting, putting some of that food together.

Ulf Ebeling (04:07)

Yeah, lovely. And I think this is important to think about that you have balance, work-life balance, whatever you might carry, whatever you might call it.

So you're very passionate about leadership. I think that's very obvious. When did it make click for you? Because you also write, we need to sort of lead and care for the people

through leadership, like we care for patients, which is, I think, always the number one priority in medicine. When did that make click for you? Because you have such a rich history. Was it like a particular moment ~ on mission or somewhere else where that really made click for you, that we need to care?

Josh Hartzell (04:46)

That's an interesting question too. I don't know that it was a particular moment. I think growing up, ~ I was involved in a lot of sports as a kid. And so when you play sports, there's a lot of teamwork involved. And I think even when I was on those teams, I recognized, I don't know at the time, I wouldn't have called it leadership, but I certainly recognized that as you sort of became one of the more,

I don't want to say necessarily better, but older kids or kids that people looked up to that you had an impact on the rest of the team. So I think even when I was in high school playing sports, there was part of that leadership role. And then, you know, I had the opportunity to do the Reserve Officer Training Corps, which is the U.S. military sort of, they pay for your college to, to once, if you do that, you join the military. So it's kind of a give and take.

But I spent those four years in college also getting taught specific leadership principles, which certainly had an impact on me from a formal educational standpoint. And then in medicine, I went to the Uniform Services University, which is the United States' military medical school. So again, sort of four more years of both formal and informal training. But I think when it really clicked was when I was a resident.

And you see this when you're in the hospital, on the wards, or in the emergency room, just how much that team-based care is important and having effective teachers or leaders, and I think we have both roles when we go in and out of them, is really important. And I was fortunate as a trainee to observe some really effective leadership. And I think for all of us, we also get the opportunity sometimes to observe some leaders that maybe aren't as effective.

As a resident, it became obvious to me that leadership was important. And then I think throughout the rest of my career, I tried to make that more of part of who I am and okay, if this is important, how do we get better? What are the things I need to do to get better, both for myself and for others?

Ulf Ebeling (06:54)

Yeah it's very interesting that you said it can already start in childhood, right, when you play a team sport, but also in the clinics. And I also like that you mentioned the different roles healthcare professionals can have, right? They might not only be treating a patient, but they might also be a teacher, leader at the same time. So it's already nice to make that very explicit and think about it like that.

But maybe also at the beginning of this conversation might be wise to talk about the definition of a leader. Because also in your book you say ~ that everyone can be a leader. But there could also be power, hierarchy, culture. So I was wondering, isn't that just a bit of an optimistic statement? Or can really everyone be a leader?

Josh Hartzell (07:37)

Yes, definitely everyone can be a leader. To me it's really important that people recognize that leadership is an activity, it's a behavior, it's not a role or a title. And I say that for a couple reasons. One is that does then empower anyone at any level to lead. ~ And I think with that it's important because then we also, when we have that knowledge that we can lead, it gives us a little more like...

responsibility to actually lead and help others. You know the definition part also I think is a very personal. ~ It's gonna be slightly different for everyone. mean, my personal definition, I wrote this in a book, is ultimately about taking care of your people so that they can take care of the mission. I think it's that simple. There's a lot in that. Most people will talk about leadership in some ways in terms of influence. How do you influence others or motivate them so that

they can accomplish the mission. They can do the task, whatever that task is. You know know, I'll give you an example of how anyone can lead. And this is one of my favorite examples of a medical student. So we were, we've had a leadership curriculum at Walter Reed National Military Medical Center for years. And during one of the sessions, one of the clerkship medical students said, well, one of the things I do is at the end of

Every day I go to my resident and I thank him or her for something they did that I appreciated and I do this because I know that the resident is working hard, which I think we would all agree and but they don't always get thanked for what they're doing and The student the student said this not my words his words I want them to one know I appreciate them, but I know that that interaction is gonna put them in a better place for their next interaction

Right, so if that resident gets that positive feedback and then maybe they go to sign out next and they're signing out their patients, they're probably gonna be a little bit kinder to everyone they interact with. Maybe they go home and they interact with their spouse or partner or kids and that positive feedback at end of the day is gonna make a difference. And I love the example because this is one student making a choice to positively impact their resident every day.

There's no reason that any medical student couldn't do something similar. There's no reason any faculty can't choose to say thank you to someone else. So to your initial question, yeah, absolutely, anyone has the ability to lead. It's just how we choose to do it.

Ulf Ebeling (10:17)

Thank you. So a completely new way for me to think about leaders, leadership, that it's more about the activity you do. And that it can be these small gestures that have huge knock-on effects downstream, not only for yourself, but those around you. So I think that's a very nice, nice story. And I was actually curious about, why is leadership important? But maybe you already answered that by saying, we care for people first, and then that improves the mission. Is that really what...

the benefit of being caring towards others is.

Josh Hartzell (10:51)

Yeah, I think it's twofold. One is that, I mean, ultimately there are people involved. Leadership is a relational activity. And the more effectively we lead, my hope would be that the more positive impact that has on the people that we're interacting with. Through that, when we have those positive interactions, that then will allow your team, if it's a small team, your department, your organization to be more effective.

And you know, there's a lot that goes into leadership, you know taking care of people, ~ maybe at the surface sounds like, ~ you're going to be nice to people and help them do things, but you know, that broader concept is: are you setting high expectations for your people? Because if I care about you Ulf, I want you to do really well. But if I'm going to set those high expectations, then I also have to be willing to, you know, hold you accountable, give you feedback, coach you through that process.

Right? If I care about my people, I have to be able to delegate effectively to give them opportunities to excel. I have to be willing to, you know, when they do great things, try to recognize them for those great things. So the taking care of people, while yes, that's sort of the main push, there's a lot that's involved in that and I think that's part of the reason why I wrote the book is it seems easy to say, but okay, what do I actually do?

And you know, the way I set this up is look, if you're not sure what to do, each chapter will tell you. There's three or four action items so that if you're not sure how to do these things, which don't necessarily come intuitively, you can just read it, look at it, and say I'm gonna focus this week on these two behaviors. And then maybe the following week I'm gonna focus on these. Or I was just having this discussion ~ actually two nights ago with a group of people I was coaching,

which is let's say that you're at work and all of a sudden you're having a problem with a certain area. Maybe you're struggling with feedback and how to give feedback to a colleague. Boom, pull out the book, read the chapter on feedback and then think about, okay, how can I apply this to this situation? Because medicine, medical education are complicated and a lot of it is on the job training and what do I need for the moment?

So having a resource that you can go to when that situation arises, I think is really important. Same thing we do with clinical care. I see an unusual infection. I'm an infectious disease physician. I haven't seen this for a while. What do I do? I go to the literature. I go to our textbooks. I try to figure out how then I apply that data. Same approach with leadership.

Ulf Ebeling (13:39)

Yeah, thank you for elaborating and this actually, maybe I need to be bit honest. When I first started reading the book, I thought, ~ it's quite lengthy and long winded. And I read it over several weeks, but that was actually the beauty of it because I was expecting to just learn about leadership, full stop, how you are a good leader. And then every chapter deals with...

a different important topic like you already just mentioned, feedback. And I realized being a tutor for first year students, I can apply most of these things even outside of a clinical context and I could even apply them to family life and other things. So it really is a sort of huge sort of collection actually of different things where you can apply it in the end. Hopefully it will make you a more caring leader, but I found it very worthwhile in a sense that it's not just about leadership. You know need to really do the

or look at the full picture and think about the full picture.

Josh Hartzell (14:41)

Yeah, no, and I appreciate that feedback. When I gave the book to the editor the first time, she was like, wow, this is a textbook. Which, you know, it's big, it's thick, but it was not written in a textbook way. So it's written more in a sort of traditional, you know, lay press book way, but I think it is intimidating to some people they see like, oh, 400 pages. But you might only need 15 of those pages this week.

Like you can break it down for what you need, when you need it. Of course you can read it straight through, but my experience, even most of the books that I've read, I keep them handy for when I need to go back to it and be like, you know what, I'm leading this change effort. Let me go back and look at that part about communicating change and what is it I need for this particular thing, and then I'm able to apply it.

Ulf Ebeling (15:32)

Yeah, and I like to usually gift on books to other people. But this one, I mean, A, it looks great with the prescription thing on the cover. But B, I'm going to be very selfish and keep this on my shelf because I think I will be referencing those chapters and it is very logically...

spread out and segmented and also at the end of every chapter those handy tips and tricks I guess in the end when once you've read it you can just come back to those and be like okay this week I'll experiment with this one way to give feedback. No, very nice, but I think this also maybe requires quite some buy-in from everyone to become a more caring leader.

One of the quotes I wrote down whilst reading your book was from, I believe, Nakita Valerio, I hope I pronounced that somewhat correctly, shouting self-care at people who actually need community care is how we fail people. It struck me, but I would love to hear from you why you included that and what it might mean for good caring leadership.

Josh Hartzell (16:35)

Yeah, and the reason why I put that in there is because a lot of times, you know, we look at burnout and we think like, oh well, if Josh could just do better self care, he would be okay. And while there is certainly, again, there is a chapter on self care and the things I can do to help myself, there's also a responsibility of us as leaders and people who create the healthcare system,

to fix processes that are causing us to be burned out, that are causing us to not be in our optimal states of health. We look at a lot of things like what's your schedule, right? Do we have humane schedules? I mean, I think in some ways, this has been, certainly in the United States, as we've went to 80-hour work weeks and other things, it's been forced on the system now. Whether every program still adheres to that, I think is still a question.

But you know that just the work scheduling and that's even as staff I talked to a lot of you know physicians who are staff who are working some pretty crazy hours or if we look at our nursing colleagues: Okay, what are your hours? What is the patient care ratio? So how many patients are you rounding on every day? What are workflow issues? So if our clinic is so inefficient that by the end of the day, I have 15 notes to write

and there was no way I could write them during the day - Well, that means I have to do all that work after clinic. And, you know, I can't remember who said this, but there was sort of this tongue in cheek joke about pajama time for primary care physicians. And that pajama time was them with their computer finishing their daily notes. So how do we as a system fix that? Right? Like we shouldn't expect physicians to be at home writing notes when they should be spending time with their families and their kids.

So that's the, look, I can't shout self-care at you and then create a system where you have to be at home doing all this work, right? The two of them don't really line up if we're being honest to each other. So it's really, we need to do both. We have to have our own self-care, whatever that is, but we have to support our healthcare team, physicians, nurses, physical therapists, pharmacists, all of them

with processes and work environments that optimize their health as well.

Ulf Ebeling (18:59)

I mean, think sounds familiar probably to a lot of listeners.

And I learned from Tasha Wyatt the other day that learners inherit a system they didn't create and they still need to deal with it. Do you maybe have any any insights on how to navigate this tension? So let's say you want to be a caring leader, right? You know give positive feedback. That's all nice and good. But what if you're really within such a system? What are ways to maybe navigate that more healthily?

Josh Hartzell (19:32)

Yeah, so I'm gonna give you a couple answers to that. One is from the leadership perspective. And that is the leader is - you have to ask your people what they need. Right, my responsibility is not to just put the self-care onus on you, but figure out how do I create an optimal work environment for you. So I need to be aware of schedules. I need to be aware of patient / nurse, patient / physician ratios.

I need to be aware of the system problems that are creating havoc for the people providing the care or the people providing the medical education. So, and you know, as a leader, that means maybe still being part of the patient care team. So I see it firsthand. It means going to medical students and asking them like, hey, tell me, tell me about your schedules. Tell me about the people you're working with. Tell me about the problems you see. So actually seeking out that data.

I think that's critical as leaders to be able to then improve the system. You know have to look for the problems. As an aside, one of the favorite questions I like to ask as a leader to sort of help create some safety, some people feel comfortable saying things is I just ask trainees, like, what drives you nuts that we're doing? Like, what are we doing that is just dumb or stupid that we should fix? And I think when you put it in that language, it gives them sort of like, 'Oh, he's serious about this.'

The other side of it then is, as a trainee medical student resident or as a faculty who is in the system, you have to be willing to give feedback. We used to always say, don't suffer in silence. So when you have leaders who are receptive or even not, try to push that up and say, look, here's the issues I'm seeing. And I love it when somebody comes to me also and says, here's the issue I'm seeing and

here's a couple potential courses of action to fix it. That's really helpful. I'm not a big fan of the like, don't bring me problems unless you're bringing me solutions. Because I think sometimes that sets up the expectation that, well, if I can't give you a couple solutions, don't bring me those problems. And what I've seen over my career, and someone actually

taught me this is, is that often those problems that don't have solutions are the ones that you need the leader the most for.

So if you can bring solutions or ideas, that's great. The last thing I'll say is, yes, there are system process and things that we need to change, but from an individual level, there are also things that you and I can do that don't require system change. We can treat each other with dignity and respect. So when I, you know, am sitting in a team room and one of my students calls a different service for a consult,

are they treated properly? Or are they getting pushed back? Or why are you calling this dumb consult? What are you guys doing? All of those things, that dignity and respect, those just interactions, we can fix that. That's in our control. It's also in our control how we listen to each other. I do both internal medicine and ID, so when I'm on the wards, like inpatient medicine wards, how do I listen to my nurses?

Like do I just go to them and be like, what's going on? What do you think's going on with this patient? Or what would help you today with this patient? I know it's a really challenging family, right? We don't need system change to listen to people, to treat each other like in a civil manner. and then we talked about gratitude earlier, like I don't need the system to change for me to go to a nurse and be like, hey, look,

like I understand how challenging that patient and their family were, like I just want to say thank you for the amazing job you did dealing with that situation. Or I want to thank you for catching that error that we put in on that medication order, that was huge. Like thank you for doing that. ~ So I think it starts with the system, but it doesn't sort of, you know, abdicate us that there aren't things we can already do to make it better.

Ulf Ebeling (23:43)

No, I think that's very true again. It sometimes is just also simply about being heard, which I think I made the connection when you said you might not have a solution when you approach your leader. It might in the end even be enough if you just spit it all out, you get it all out, you already feel better, right? So quite often it's also just about being heard or your leaders being aware about the issues and then maybe they can help you, maybe it's not even required.

I think that these feedback loops need improving and we can play our role in improving and I think this is a beautiful thing to already for students to take away. It's very annoying when you get shouted at at the phone for a stupid question, right? But maybe later on when you're the one getting the call, don't do that same response. Yeah, yeah, very, very.

Josh Hartzell (24:37)

Yes, that's

a great point Ulf. Well, if mean someone can break that cycle, right? And we often do things. mean, I think you were talking about the hidden curriculum. We do things we've seen other people do and it just becomes what people do. But yeah, we have the choice to be the end of that cycle of, you know what? When that medical student calls me, I'm gonna be like, oh great, what year are you? What are you doing? Cool, tell me what you need. We can make that as individuals much better within our system.

And we've known this for years, but yet we still see it happen.

Ulf Ebeling (25:08)

I think after so many years you just adopt all those habits and values that are around. In terms of, you already mentioned a few ways of being a caring leader, the one I think resonated most with me reading the book was ~ CBWA, care by walking around. It's a bit of a mouthful the abbreviation, but the concept of just being there and listening ~ I think is...

Fantastic. Those educators, professors, faculty who've just knocked on the door, who've come by, who just wanted to grab a cup of coffee. For me at least, it's always been transformative conversations, rejuvenating, giving me energy. For me at least, also these moments are just so beautiful and then it's really not about valuations through money or other things. It's really about you feel seen and heard as a human being.

And I think most people in medicine are there for connection, helping people and not necessarily for other incentives. I think describing that is very good. I don't know if you have some more insights about what it should look like in practice. ~ But yeah, I think it's a great slogan at least.

Josh Hartzell (26:26)

Yeah, and that was by ~ these two gentlemen, Kuzas and Posner, who wrote a book called Leadership Challenge, as well as some others. I was fortunate. I actually had a lot of leaders when I was early in my career that did this. ~ And I think that made it more real to me, especially then when I read about it heard other people doing it. But I would agree with you, right? So if you're...

If you're a mid or senior, it doesn't matter what level leader you are. I think being with your people is really important. If you're someone who's teaching the basic sciences, do you ever just show up where the students are studying and just ask them how they're doing and check in on them? Do you ever just drop in on the anatomy lab during maybe study hours to see if anybody needs any help or just simply like, hey, what's going on? How are you guys doing?

Those connections are really, really important. There are also opportunities where you can get information and find out, like, hey, what are you guys struggling with? you're

struggling with that? Maybe I didn't explain that well enough. ~ Or I think of our teams that are on the wards or in the ERs or ORs or whatever, and they work long hours. Just go by and see how they're doing. Just check in on them.

And again, that's an opportunity to thank them for the work they're doing. Like, hey, I appreciate it. You know guys are doing some amazing stuff. Like, I heard you had a really tough case. Everybody doing okay? ~ Or just simply to say hi. Like, hey, I'm not here for anything. Just walking through the hospital checking on folks. You know know, just a reminder if there's ever things that I can do to help you to make the system better. Like, please, I'm open for it.

I think when you see somebody personally, it's just different than if somebody sends an email and they're like, yes, tell me your problems, or you're in a big town hall. ~ I mean, I had some really exemplars of this, ~ Major General Jeff Clark, who I wrote about in the book and interviewed. I mean, he was our hospital director or commander at the time, and he would just come in on like Saturdays and kind of walk around the hospital and just check in on people. A little bit unnerving, I think, to many, because he was a general officer at the time,

and he would like come into our team room and sit down on a couch, all civilian clothes, so it wasn't like he was wearing his uniform and his stars. He would just sit down and be like, hey, how's everyone doing? What's going on? But people really appreciated that, and people would tell him. It would be a Saturday morning or Saturday afternoon, and they'd be like, yes, sir, this is broken. But that's the only way we'd find out about it.

And I think people just also appreciated the fact that this person who's at this level was willing to spend a little extra time coming to see how we're doing. ~ Yeah, presidents care about walking around. It goes a long ways.

Ulf Ebeling (29:25)

So what I've heard now is it's very nice when you're a caring leader, right, to the others around you. It can really transform healthcare for the better. But it might even be that you could look at it from a selfish perspective, right? Like it gives me better data, what I now heard, right? It gives me more insights in what's actually going on. And I also think...

we probably should do some research about coffee machines, because I always realize that coffee machines, like different teams meet, they exchange ideas, suddenly it makes click because you get a new perspective about an issue or research question you didn't quite know how to address. Yeah, in the end, it's all about connection and that really seems to be a great catalyst. Yeah, yeah.

Josh Hartzell (30:10)

Yeah, well, and I love your point, the connection catalyst, because there's a lot of data coming out now that having connection at work is really important for people's wellbeing. And to your point, yeah, it fosters discussion. I can't remember who was doing this, but I recently read that this one hospital had a coffee cart, and they would actually push the coffee cart around and go to different places and offer people coffee, but on each of the coffee cups,

there was a question that would prompt discussion and it wasn't about work, was like, tell me about your pets or who's your favorite sports team or what's your favorite book. And so as people would share and drink their coffee, they would also have these questions to get to know each other a little bit better. So I was like, this is a wonderful idea. One, because I like coffee ~ and two, because yeah, it created that catalyst for discussion.

Ulf Ebeling (31:03)

Wonderful. You know also, this might be unrelated, but it might be related. You know wrote about that sort of the culture, the leadership culture maybe, is shaped by either the actions taken or the lack of actions within an organization. Is that then pretty much this, whether someone is quiet and hidden away or if someone is in touch with the staff?

Josh Hartzell (31:26)

So for the actions and inactions, to me it's really important for us to know that we can be proactive and we can do certain things and if I give you an opportunity and then coach you and give you feedback, that's an active process. The inactions really I think for me are things like, I saw you disrespect a nurse and I just let it go. I saw somebody yell at medical student or

treat them poorly and I just let it go because when we let those things go those inactions then become what our culture is. Like if we allow those things to happen that perpetuates it and in over time that just becomes the accepted norm: It's okay when I call for a consult to be disrespectful to the person on the other end, It's okay not to show up to meetings on time because well, that's just every what everyone does.

You know know the favorite line I have and I looked at this the other day, it's think unknown who really said it first is like what you permit you promote. So if you allow things to happen and you have inaction that then becomes the accepted behavior whether you intended that or not. So I think for us as leaders it's really important that we think about that. We have to, one be proactive but also when we see things that we don't like we have to fix them because if we don't fix them,

that becomes the culture.

Ulf Ebeling (32:56)

Wow, so I was also like, if you say something, you give negative feedback, right? If you have a, let's call it a bad situation, you give negative feedback to hopefully improve it. But also by not saying anything, you also give indirectly feedback that it's okay. I've never thought about it like that, yeah. And then I guess sort of taking the high road takes more energy and is more risky, but in the end it will, yeah, you don't even know what it will benefit, maybe just a student or...

a junior doctor or maybe even the patient in the end who gets better treatment, faster treatment and who knows what the knock-on effects are. So these small acts can really really have huge down downward effects in the positive or in the negative sense.

Josh Hartzell (33:39)

Yeah,

Both. And I think your point there, right, the lack of feedback is still feedback. And for me, I do think that it's twofold. If I give you feedback about you being maybe rude to a nurse or something, hopefully that corrects your behavior. But then also everyone who watches you in the future when you no longer have that behavior sees what right looks like. If I don't correct it,

Everyone then when they see you treating people disrespectfully also sees that and then potentially they perpetuate it. So even these small interactions, because each of us interacts with so many other people, can have a huge ripple effect in our organizations.

Ulf Ebeling (34:26)

Yeah, wonderful. I think it's great to think about it that way. And I think it's already become very clear that even just learners, people just entering a system can already have small acts of caring leadership towards other. Is there any other particular things you advise? ~

people beginning in the healthcare world or wherever they might be working to practice along the way. So even if they don't have sort of a formal leadership role in their title.

Josh Hartzell (35:00)

Yeah, a couple things. The first off, and I used to do this with our interns when I was the intern director for our hospitals, so all the new trainees who would come, and I would just tell them just to observe. We have free leadership education in front of us every day. Just watch the people you're working with and specifically watch them like, what did Josh do that was effective as a leader or as a teacher? Because I think you can do the same with your teaching skills.

What of those skills do I want to use when I am in that position where I will be leading or teaching? So simply be by watching and reflecting and thinking, we can improve our

leadership a lot. And to me, it's like, what are those skills do I put in my tool belt? And what are those skills do I say I absolutely do not want to do that as a leader? So that's the first thing. It's easy, but if we do it, we learn a ton over time.

The second point would be, and I call this being a student of leadership, and you're never done being a student of leadership. So over the course of your medical career, your business career, whatever, make it a habit to study some leadership consistently. And look, medical students are really busy. Trainee, like residents and trainees who are in, they're really busy. Faculty, everyone's really busy. But,

do you not have 30 minutes somewhere, once a week, once a month where you could listen to a great podcast? I mean, potentially like this one. Or do you have 30 minutes a month that you could pick up and read one chapter of a book? I find it hard to believe that people can't find 30 minutes somewhere. And if you do 30 minutes a month over the course of years, that adds up.

Right, that really adds up. So instead of thinking about it in terms of, oh, I need to get a degree in leadership or I need an MBA or I don't have time to read all these books, just do it in incremental chunks. And what you'll see is that if you do that, you know, after a few months or a year, it really makes a difference. And, you know, being that student of leadership over time, it's never too early to start. You know know, for medical students, I would ask them, think about

what are the skills I need to do to be really successful as a medical student or as a resident? Read about followership. How do you be an effective follower to support your team? What are those skills? Because if I know those skills and I do them well, boy, my residents are going to love me. My attendings are going to love me, right? Which is then going to help you be more successful at that level. And then, OK, maybe your next level, I need to learn about feedback. I'm a resident and now I'm giving feedback to students.

How do I do that? What does it look like? Like read, you know, read about that. But yeah, I think it's important that one, we just watch and observe people. And then two, like put it on your schedule. Make it a habit to 30 minutes a month. That's all I'm asking, right? Maybe you have more, but at least something, it'll pay off. It'll pay off for you and pay off for us collectively as a healthcare, you know, system.

Ulf Ebeling (38:21)

Yeah, it's really shockingly obvious really. So thank you for writing it so clearly and also explaining it to us now. Sometimes the silence says more than a lot of words, not having feedback also is feedback. That's very interesting.

And also what about you said about making the time. think nowadays we could also just say maybe a few minutes of your scrolling time on social media. Imagine if you invested

that in the people around you rather than in a big tech company, that might be a better investment maybe. But also I used to say myself, I don't have the time. And at some point I became aware of that statement and what it means. And I think in the end we have the time. It's just how we choose to spend our time.

So I try to be very mindful of that myself. But maybe to come back to these negative instances, something that baffles me as a medical student is we have this wonderful healthcare system where we all work together, right? Every specialization is a small puzzle piece and we're all there to help the patient. But quite often the narratives about the other special...

specializations are quite negative, right? The ER doctor saying the radiologist is slow, lazy, whatever it might be, and the radiologist saying the ER doctor ordering unnecessary CT scans. And ~ I mean, it's always easy to complain. But also, I rarely see healthcare professionals sort of fight for each other.

And then I read a statement in your book about grenades. Maybe you can enlighten us a little bit what we can maybe learn from the military on that, how to really fight for each other.

Josh Hartzell (40:13)

Yeah. And the quote from the book is that like, you know, people don't usually die for like their country. They die for the people standing right to the right and left of them. Right. In the military, it's really about my fellow soldiers, sailors, airmen and Marines and the relationships and bonds we have, which is similar in healthcare. Although we work with a lot of different people and we don't necessarily have that same level of connection. The ask I would have people think about is, but we're all on the same team.

Whether you're a surgeon, an ER doc, a pathologist, a radiologist, an internal, a nurse, a so we're all on the same team. So how do we treat each other or have that same bond? Your point about the way we talk about people. So I learned this lesson, ~ boy, I don't know, it's a while ago, but I worked with Jessica Cervi, who's our associate dean for faculty affairs now. She was our associate dean for faculty development at the time.

And this would come up in teaching sessions where someone would sort of make a offhand or snide comment about a different service and she would always correct it. And not only would she correct it, but when we were doing our, like sort of teaching people how to teach, we would bring this up and talk to them about, look, when you see somebody in morning report complaining about the emergency room and how they made this decision and how could they possibly do this?

We can't let that happen. We can't let other physicians, educators talk negatively about other ones. Because what that does is it, going back to our former point, is it perpetuates

that and it makes it seem like that's okay. So the big way we fix that is we have to give people feedback on that. Honestly, this is probably one of the things I see a lot either when I'm on the wards or ~

during teaching sessions is people will say like, I can't believe that outside hospital, they were so dumb that they would do this. and I'm like, hold on a second. These are other physicians who are doing their best to make the best decisions. We really shouldn't talk about them that way. But you have to stop and correct people for that. Or, ~ the ER didn't do anything on this workup again. I can't believe they're sending this patient and there's no workup done. And I'm like, okay, well, you know,

let's step back for a second. Do you think they're doing the best they can for their patients based on the system and what they're dealing with? We did not allow that kind of behavior because as soon as we do, then it creates those barriers between us. And the other thing I try to remind people, and this is both for clinical care, teaching, and leadership, is everyone shows up trying to do their best job. They may not be effective in our eyes,

and we may not be effective in their eyes, but we all show up generally trying to do our best. I mean, yes, there are outliers who are just maybe not, but that's really an outlier situation. Recognize best intent in people instead of thinking the worst. We tend to go to the worst, like, they're a terrible physician or I can't believe it. Just best intent, like they're doing the best they can trying to help you, and guess what? My job is to help you.

How can I help you be more effective? Because we both, again, you mentioned this, Ulf, like we all want the same thing, which what is best for our patients. We also, as faculty and teachers, we want what is best for our students. We might have different views on how to get there, but we need to remind each other that we have a common vision and that we're on the same team. And that starts with not allowing some of this negative talk about each other.

Ulf Ebeling (44:07)

Yeah, it's actually, if you think about it, very unique what we have in healthcare, that we have the shared commitment, the shared goal, and everyone contributes that, and it might be with different educational backgrounds on different levels at different times, but we all, trying to move in one direction together. Yeah.

Josh Hartzell (44:25)

And I just add one thing to that, Ulf, is that in the military we talk about ~ what do you see from your foxhole, right? Which is kind of like you dig out and you're in a defensive position and you're looking out of your foxhole. So I can only see a limited area. But the people to the right of me and left of me, they have different views, they see different

things. And for us in healthcare, this is really important. Look, I'm an infectious disease physician. The way I see things is different

than maybe one of my surgical colleagues who's consulting me on a particular infection. Like, they're in the OR, they see things, they treat patients. What we need to do is step back and ask people, hey, help me understand why you wanna do this for the patient. Because lo and behold, occasionally, they're actually right and we're actually wrong. Right, because we just don't have their perspective.

So if we again recognize, we both want the same thing for this patient, let me just stop for a second. Hey Ulf, help me understand why you wanna do this. Help me understand why you don't wanna do this procedure or why you do wanna do it or why you don't wanna give antibiotics. But like just have a discussion about it and really be open. Again, this goes back to the listening. I think often we're "listening" but we've already got our mind made up. Can I go into that situation with some humility

and listen and try to figure out, hey, you know what? Like I actually got this wrong. I need to change. Maybe the way we're teaching our medical students in a particular course is wrong and we need to listen to them and think like, you know what? Like they're actually right. This, that would make more sense. So yeah, common vision, being humble and then listening, really listening, I think are critical for leaders, teachers, parents, spouses, partner, like everybody.

Ulf Ebeling (46:19)

Yeah, that's what I already said when reading the book. I think you can apply it anywhere.

to improve almost anything. So that's what makes it extra valuable. But I agree that, and the humility is also part of the culture, right? It's counterintuitive to take ~ humility standpoint, right? It's also the students, I think, often feel this sort of imposter syndrome, having to perform, having to uphold some sort of image of knowing everything, whereas they simply can't. And we all know this, and we all went through it or go through it. So yeah.

I think we also maybe need to change how we deal with when someone says, don't know, it may be compliment that, that they can admit that and so on. Yeah, yeah. So this all sounds sounds very good, but I'm also trying to take the critics perspective who might say, yeah, well, Josh, all well and good all sounds very nice, but we're just gonna get like soft individuals,

who are not gonna really do their work, trying to find ways out. And also then I can't say anything more, I can't give any more critical feedback. But in your book, actually, you sort of argue the exact opposite. You know say by doing this caring leadership, you can set

even higher or extremely high expectations. And that sort of, yeah, I think leadership acts as a sort of buffer to deliver even better care

and that it allows you to give even tougher feedback than originally. Could you maybe give some insights into that for those who are still not quite sold on why this might be the right approach to leadership?

Josh Hartzell (47:55)

Yeah, one of my favorite quotes from the people I interviewed was Amy Vertrees, who's a surgeon, and I think most people argue that surgeons are not soft, said that caring for people as leaders is monumental strength. And to your point, ~ have you ever worked for a jerk? How motivated are you to work for somebody who treats you poorly? How effective is that in a learning environment

when someone is yelling at you or treating you, you can't learn in that environment. You know can't take care of patients in that environment. So I would argue that if we're not caring for people, we're really missing the opportunity cost of what we really potentially could do. ~ And you're right, the way I've sort of framed this or think about it is, if you know I care about you and really care about you, one,

you don't want to let me down. I mean I think of the leaders who I respected the most, who, you know, provided opportunities for me, helped me become a better clinician or a better educator, gave me some really hard feedback. I would do anything for them, right? But they didn't shy away from like, hey, Josh, you're not meeting the standard here. Like, I'm really disappointed that, you know, you keep showing up for meetings late.

Like that's not what I would have expected of you and it's not what we expect of our leadership team.

Is that soft? Right? You know know, and to me, the thing that makes that more, I don't wanna say easier, because giving people tough feedback is always gonna be hard, but if you know that I have your best interests at heart, like at the end of the day, if that student, resident, faculty, whoever I'm giving feedback to, like we've built that relationship where you know that I really care about you,

then I can tell you that you're messing up. Because you'll accept it a little bit better because you already trust me. But if I'm the guy or girl who's been yelling at you and treating you terribly and I give you feedback, you're probably just gonna discount it. Because you don't even respect me. So I think you create that bond and that relationship and then that allows you to give that feedback and people are more receptive of it. On the flip side,

If I really care about you, Ulf, and I know that you're doing something that's gonna be detrimental to your career or professional development,

I have to give you that feedback. Like if, because if I care about you, I don't want to see you mess up. I don't want to see you a year from now make a huge mistake and and me think to myself, yeah I saw that. I could have, I could have told him that. I knew he was doing that. So it makes us as leaders when we care about people have to step into that discomfort and give the feedback. The question I always ask myself is

this is really awkward, it's gonna be really challenging, but I care about Ulf so I'm gonna give him this feedback. Because I would feel bad if I didn't. Right? ~ Similarly I think as people who receiving feedback, we also need to have some perception of, you know, my leader, my teacher, whoever is giving me this feedback because they care about me.

Right? That's why they're giving me this view. Because we're often resistant to feedback. You know know, again, if I'm always yelling at you and treating you like garbage, well, you're probably not gonna feel that way. So I think it's really important, but yeah, I don't think it's soft. I think a lot of these things are actually harder to do than it'd be easy for me to not give you the feedback. I just avoid it. Then we don't have to have the discussion. It's not good for you. It's not good for our organization.

But boy, makes me, it's way easier for me at the time, certainly. It may create problems down the road, but it's easier to avoid that situation. So yeah, I don't think there's anything soft about it.

Ulf Ebeling (52:12)

No, it would have also been easier for you not to write the book. Yet you did. So, no, I think it makes sense, but I think these things and feedback in the interpersonal things, they can have a sort of connotation of being soft or not really relevant, whereas I think it's now becoming very clear how relevant and important they are. And once again, if it is just in your own interest that the people you lead carry out your mission,

build the relationship first and the rest will follow and they will give you the right data for you to make future decisions on and they will carry out the mission even better than you might have even envisioned. So I think that's the take home and also hard feedback, I remember you wrote about I think a resident who was prolonged, in the book, to stay longer because there were some concerns about quality and stuff and

you outline very nicely what that process looked like and how hard it was, but that it was worthwhile for everyone in the end. So I think we touched on a lot of things. We already had quite some insights for current leaders, but also for students, upcoming leaders, small acts of leadership. So is there maybe a sort of final advice

or question that you would like to leave learners and educators with. Ultimately we're all leaders or we'll even become a former leader at some point. But I'm sure you probably still have something to give us.

Josh Hartzell (53:50)

~ I would say two things. One is that, you know, that we can demystify leadership, its behavior, and we can be intentional about it. So what are the intentional acts that I can do to more effectively lead, right? We talked about many. I can listen. I can be humble. I can give feedback. But we can be intentional about those acts. So the more we think about it and learn about it, it allows us to have that intentionality behind it.

The second thing that I'll end with, and I think this is critical for us as humans, not just physicians or educators or learners, is that every day, every interaction we have, we have the opportunity to positively impact the life of the person who is in front of us. So the way I treat you, the way I interact with you, I can have a positive impact on your life.

So what would it, My question is, what would it look like if all of us approached our interactions with that intent in mind? How can I positively impact the life of the person in front of me? And if we have that intent in mind, I suspect that our cultures will improve, our lives will improve, and certainly patient care will be driven by that as well. So I think that's the question, how do I make people's lives better? What is that action I need to take to help this person?

Ulf Ebeling (55:18)

Thank you very much. think that's a very nice note to end on. And I think also you've given excellent instructions on how to read this book. Again, I think the entire book and everything we discussed is brilliant, but what I love most is still the cover, the actual prescription. And I think the recommendation is that this is a very slow read. Put it in your office, put it next to your bed, and read it bit by bit, even if you're "just" a learner.

It can probably help you treat your patients better, have better relationship with your family, with your colleagues, whatever you might try to improve in your life.

Josh Hartzell (56:00)

Yeah, and we're definitely all learners at every stage of our career. And I definitely appreciate the opportunity to have some great questions and chat with your audience. So thank you so much.

Ulf Ebeling (56:12)

Yeah, and thank you for engaging with learners directly. It's been very interesting to read and chat to you, so thank you. And I hope we have an incoming generation of caring leaders ahead of us, because in the end we'll probably be in hospital at some point and be treated by the generation of physicians we get to train. yeah, thank you very much.

Josh Hartzell (56:40)
Thank you, take care.

END OF TRANSCRIPT